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Research Article

**AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON THE POPULATION OF
PAKISTAN ABOUT CERVICAL CANCER**

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Abstract:

Cervical cancer is considering the three rising causes of cancers among the womens all over the world. Cervical cancer is also considering the three major causes of deaths among the women, nearly 80 percent of developing countries suffer from it. The current research is about the approach and practical survey were conducted to conclude the attitude & practices for Pakistani womens population concerning cervical cancer screening. Through comfortable sampling, one ninety-two spacemen were inducted and carry out a pre-tested and structured analysis. Nearly five percent of patients know that screening was conducted for cervical cancer. Pap test had carried out for only 2.6 percent of sample. Pap test was not conducted for all patient due to the lack of information about it. In final result, the Pakistani community examined here indicated a very low approach of the Pap test and a limited ability respecting its service.

Key Words: *Perceptions, cervical, Pap Test, Screening, Malignancies.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Cervical cancer considers one of the most frequent malignancies in the women all our world (1). Its contribution to cancer burden is significant across all cultures and economies. In recent survey about 270,000 deaths occur by cervical cancer in whole world, mostly the less developed regions more face with this problem (1). Mostly the ratio of mortality due to cervical cancer increasing in developing countries because the developing countries spend only five percent resources globally on cancer (2). This is note, that many resources were expended on a cancer worldwide. Pakistan also faces a dual difficulty of diseases like other less developed countries. According to age standardized incidence rate (ASIR) cervical cancer is the 4th most frequent cancer in the Pakistani women with an of six.5 percent 100,000 (3). In Pakistan the frequency on cervical cancer is less than many other western countries, but the mortality ratio was higher. The increasing rate of mortality is due to late overnice of cervical cancer in Pakistan (4).

The early stages of cervical cancer were examined by the help of Pap test and due to this the frequency and mortality ratio of cervical cancer is decreased in developed countries as compared to the developing countries (5). In less developed countries, however, it has had little impact due to an inadequate coverage (a low proportion of women who have a smear). With this approach, this research studies were conducted to regulate the awareness and practices of a Pakistani women community respecting cervical cancer screening.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This research study was carried out in the year of 2018 in Mayo Hospital Lahore. Those patients were excluded from study who suffers from cervical cancer, supra cervical or gynecological issue. All the participant of this study was informed orally. This research study was conducted under the approval of Review Committee of the Center for health research, Islamabad.

RESULTS:

Before test structured survey was conducted to collect information. The substance legitimacy of overview things was inspected by clinical specialists and companion survey. Other than account the statistic (\$250) none had history of any danger. The statistical data is abridged in Table 1. About 85% (163) of the members concurred that early recognition of cancer improves survival. 36 % (69) of the example had caught wind of cervical cancer. About 5% (10) subjects realized that screening is accessible for cervical cancer. Just 2.6% (5) had ever had a pap test. The most widely recognized reason referred to for not having had a pap test, was absence of data about it (Table 2). Over 70% subjects demonstrated distinct fascination for getting additional data with respect to cervical cancer screening. Some 54% trusted that the Pap test would be difficult About 95% (182) uncovered that they have never been proposed by a specialist to have a Pap test.

Table 1. Demographic Features of the Pakistani Female Population Surveyed

	Percentage	(N)
Marital Status	80.7 percent	155
Married	19.3 percent	37
Single	64.6 percent	
Place of Residence Urban	35.4 percent	124
Rural	44.3 percent	68
Education		
Nil	47.4 percent	85
School	8.3 percent	91
University	80.2 percent	16
Occupation		
Housewife	15.6 percent	154
Working	4.2 percent	30
Student	4.2 percent	8
Monthly income		
<5,000	59 percent	114
5,000-9,999	26 percent	50
10,000-14,999	9.9 percent	19
>15,000	4.7 percent	9

192 patients (all women) were become the part this research. The average age of all patients was 42 years (SD: 14 years). Approximately 81 percent (155) females were married. 44% (85) patients had

uneducated. Approximately 64.9 percent (124) lived in urban areas. The monthly income of about 94.9% patient had not more than 15,000 RS.

Table 2. Attitudes of the Pakistani Female Population Surveyed Regarding Cervical Cancer

	%	(n)
What is the reason for not having had a pap test?		
Never heard about it	50.50 percent	97
No need to get it	37.5 percent	72
Never asked by doctor	3.6 percent	7
Facility not available	3.1 percent	6
Do you need more information about cervical cancer screening?		
Very much	28.6 percent	55
Much	42.2 percent	81
Not much	19.3 percent	37
Not at all	8.9 percent	17
Are you comfortable with Pap test		
Very much	9.4 percent	18
Much	35.4 percent	68
Not much	35.4 percent	68
Not at all	17.2 percent	33

In the current research not more than 14 percent patient were notice that cancer can detected through screening from it early stage (6). In the same research, only seven percent patient recorded to have been learned about the cancer screening by a doctor - a finding consistent with our results.

All patients in our research expired intense significance in taking more knowledge about cervical cancer. This positive approach is hopeful trend in the people. That, however, goes only part of the way towards increasing the use of cervical cancer screening. various research in developed community have achieved that even in the higher socio-economic strata of South Asian female, the Pap test ratio comparatively lower due to lack of information (7). That is the way; increasing the awareness of the people concerning cervical cancer screening consider one of the more significant steps in improving Pap test coverage in the Pakistani women. Any organized cancer screening endeavor is unlikely to achieve without sound information in the suffered people concerning its goals & adequacy. Many inexpensive, countries based approach have been determining to increase the knowledge regarding cervical neoplasia screening (8), which may be working in Pakistan. Moreover, the physicians required to prepare and informed their participant about such screening

tests.

DISCUSSION:

Data for this research were collected from PIMS Hospital Islamabad. Statistic characteristics of the research sample typically related to the community of a developing country with maximum of community having a less monthly income sources and proficiency. Cervical cancer is in the three most frequent causes of cancer deaths worldwide. Approximately 85 percent death due to cervical cancer worldwide occurs in developing countries; cervical cancer is considering serious cause of cancer deaths (1). The age regulated death ratio (ASMR) for cervical cancer in developing courtiers is nearly 12/100,000 with respect to ASMR of 4.00 / 100,000 in more developed countries (9). The increasing rate of mortality is due to late overnice of cervical cancer in these countries. In Pakistan, more than 70% malignancies present in advanced stages (10). In a current research from Islamabad, <1% of cervical cancer could be identify as before-cancer attack (stage 0). In the same way, only 12 percent of the cervical cancers could be identifying at Stage 1st (4). This slow awareness of the cervical neoplasia increases the mortality ratio.

Pap test was conducted for the screening of cervical cancer this is most effective test for the detecting of

cervical cancer at a very starting stage. In our research spacemen, Pap test was conducted only for 2.6 percent patient. This is in comparison to the data from many other more developed world (Canfell et al reported from several developed countries (11). From the National Health analysis, more than 80 percent of women had conducted Pap test in US from past three years (12). Implementing a coordinated screening intervention of such magnitude however, has seemed far from practical in majority of developing nations, including Pakistan. In Pakistan the coverage of Pap test is lowers the major reasons is lack of knowledge about cancer screening. Our 85 percent research participant suggested that early analysis of cancer improve the life chance, very limited information was available for cervical cancer screening. Pap test was not conducted because due to the lack of knowledge about it, or about its performance economic restraint or availability as is often identified. Information, the survey assessed the knowledge, approach and practical of patients respecting the screening of cervical cancer (13). Analysis was putted and process by the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences 13.0 (SPSS 13.0). Actual statistics of socio-demographic data, information, approach and practical of patients respecting screening of cervical cancer were resolved and reported in the forms of mean, standard deviation, proportions and %.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, in this research we examined here a very less approach of the Pap test and poor information concerning its utility. The more common reason of not received Pap test was the lack of information of Pap test in our community. Motivating the awareness of people concerning cervical cancer screening is increase before a coordinated cancer screening program could be imposed in Pakistan.

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